

STUDY ON ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR AND ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST AMONG THE EMPLOYEES OF IT COMPANIES, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

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Abstract

The current research has investigated the connection between specific administrative- factors such as perceived organizational support (POS), procedural justice (PJ) and communication, as determinants of organizational trust (OT) and their effect on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). The records were gathered from 205 informants from different managerial levels of various companies in IT zone. Quality scales were engaged to evaluate organizational trust (OT) and its precursor and subsequent elements. The result showed that former variables help in intensifying the degree of OT. The available of OT is positively combined with all the proportions of OCB as said by the workers of the organization. Therefore, it was recommended that enterprises should promote the procedure yielding to belief in organization, so that workers are better involved in additional character action leading in improved single and organizational efficacy.

Keywords: Communication, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Organizational Trust, Perceived Organizational Support, Procedural Justice.

INTRODUCTION

There is a significant change in company structure, tasks, procedure and action of workers by structural reforms. It has been identified that there is an overall decrease of faith in the company among the workers because of organizational terms and structural adaptations. According to Shaw (1997), workers belief is an important phase of ambitious exchanges existing in an enterprise for its victory, and helps to build and maintain a trusting relationship between managers and professionals. Many reports have claimed that distrust and subsequent issues in all kinds of companies. (Ferris & Travaglione, 2005). Investigators have researched a number of constituents related with organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) (Konvosky & Pugh, 1995), organizational justice (Crorpanzano & Randall, 1994; Lind & Tyler, 1989;) and perceived organizational effectiveness, such as organizational support (POS) (Davis, 1990). There is an insufficiency of literature in the region of confidence in administration and decreased consciousness has been given to the connection of organizational trust (OT), its precursor and subsequent elements. Once more, the literature does not give adequate proof, regarding the expanse to which these factors are influential in deciding OT, thus determining the organizational citizenship behavior of workers. This research is look forward to analyses

the understanding of OT and its connection with administrative-level variables and its effect on OCB in Indian aesthetic conditions.

Organizational citizenship behavior

The connection between faith in an enterprise and OCB has been analyzed in many reports. Organ (1990) examined OCB and the reciprocal confidence that bears social exchange connections guarantee that OCB will be reflected in the long duration. Lester and Brower (2003) researched that employee's insight of their head trust in them affected their work performance and OCB. Reports of Tyler and Blader (2004) and Gould-Williams (2003) found that faith at the same time affects organizational citizenship behaviors.

Only certain researches have analyzed the effect of OT on various proportions of OCB in Indian companies, so it requires additional analysis. Therefore, it is a proof from the researches that OT is emphatically connected to PJ, POS, communication and OCB. However, the part of belief in the Asian circumstances with PJ, POS and proportions of transmission as fortunetellers and OCB as result persists unexamined.

Organizational trust

Higher level of trust will help to motivate the workers with regard to company and administrative targets instead of single intentions, was researched by Mishra, 1995. The research offers to survey the constituent variables affecting OT, such as procedural justice, POS, communication and union of faith with OCB. (Sonnenberg 1994) examined that distrust will result in poor decision making by team members, increase in stress levels, employees will lose the focus on work and being less active and avoid challenges; at the workplace.

Procedural justice

Honest processes manifest that the employees are handled as ends instead of means. The workers may see honest process as bouncing back institutional ethics. Procedures are considered to have a more enduring quality but Outcomes are viewed as it is happening only once said Tyler in 1990. The usage of ceremoniously equitable customs results in more sophisticated problems, such as workers responsibility to the company and faith in its officials. Leventhal (1980) examined that processes are valued, positioned on their steadiness of petition, existing social excellence and the standard of their partiality, validity, fix ability. Therefore, it is declared that the essential features of Procedural justice can change, but the essence of administrative potency are steady in the company. Thus, if a company employs honest processes once, they are trusted to utilize sincere processes persistently chief workers to trust that the company can be believed to work in distant future. (Knovsky & Pugh, 1994). The findings of Hubbell and Chory-Assad (2005) suggested that PJ was the strongest predictor of OT compared to all the other forms of justice.

Perceived Organizational Support

Perceived organizational support is nothing but the workers observe that they are evaluated by their companies about their welfare (Eisenberger, Huntington & Sowa 1985). The organization confirms that the assist will be accessible from the company whenever required by the workers

so that it helps to carry out one's job effectively and also to deal with stressful situations (George, Reed, & Fielding, 1993).

The Perceived organizational support and faith theoretical linkages are positioned on social exchange theory (Blau, 1964). Workers will be sincere to the company if they perceive that their company is sympathetic to them (Setton, & Liden, 1996). The organization will notice and reward employees' when the employee perform an action that is beneficial to the organization. The workers trust that the company estimates their benefaction and bothers for their welfare when the constructive task expertise's is delivered by the company and also it helps to bring about belief with regard to the company.

It was established that companies are administering the workers broadening agendas and improving the production of employees and giving guaranty on promotions have an important constructive effect on worker's eye view of organizational assist (Wayne, Shore &, 1997).

Communication

The companies give relevant information to employees about the company, is known to be open and accurate communication which helps to describe the thinking beyond the administration and human resource (HR) choices and cheer worker's association (Caudron, 2002). Elsbach and Elofson (2000) explained that the elite of analytic -based faith in the peak administration is matured to the workers who are well enlightened about company procurements, it helps to enhance the pellucidity and trust between workers and organization. Gilbert and Tang (1999) found that if a particular worker is fragment of the communication channel, who is giving important particulars, then the individual is more probably to expertise OT. The worker's directness and involvement encourages the workers to recognize their company (Smidts & Van Riel, 2001). The workers expand an elite of analytic-based faith towards the organization in the top administration who are informed about organizational achievements (Elsbach & Elofson, 2000). Brodt and Whitener (2002) found that when controllers transferred publicly with and in a crystal clear way and established responsibility, it does not result contradictory result of a dispute between a worker and a manager. Therefore, faith can be evolved through expanding the standard of communication. The communication and faith is escorted by social exchange theory, where the communication gives workers a constructive emotion about the organization, and it helps to enrich confidence in management. Most of the analysis have concentrated on mutual faith in OT from communication. Consequently, the current analysis targets to examine the wide appearance of communication, that is, frankness and correctness related to belief on company.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study measures the connection between perceived organizational support (POS), procedural justice (PJ) and communication, as determinants of organizational trust (OT) and their impact on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB).

The following hypotheses were formulated to examine the relationship between OCB and OT.

- H1: Procedural justice, ACC, OP and POS from the worker would conclude in belief towards the company.
- H2: OCB would consequently forecast Organizational trust.
- H3: The connection between PJ, POS, OP & ACC and factors of OCB would mediate the Organizational trust.

Sample

This is an integral part of research design. This study uses both types of data. Viz. primary and secondary. The study was carried out with sample survey of 205 respondents from different managerial levels of various companies in IT sector through stratified random sampling. The data were collected through mail as well as directly. A total of 320 questionnaires were distributed, out of which 260 were returned. Out of these questions, 54 had to be eliminated because of lost evidence and the general trial size is 206. Out of the total specimens, 42 percent managers belonged to high levels, 24 percent belonged to middle levels and 34 percent belonged to lower levels of pecking order. The average age of the participants was 25-30 years. The survey was completed throughout a period of 1 month.

Data and Analysis

A draft questionnaire was developed on the basis of comprehensive reviews. The questionnaire is classified into two types. Part 1 consists of question seeking information about employee characteristics which include age, educational qualifications, experience, cadre. The part 2 includes questions that aim at obtaining details such as Organizational trust, procedural justice, perceived organizational support, communication, organizational citizenship behavior. This survey is conducted by using five point Likert scale. The study employed statistical tool such as Chi Square, correlation, and spss software is used to analyses the data.

Sem Model

Hypothesis

- There is a significant relationship between PJ 1 and OT.
- There is a significant relationship between CO1 and OT.
- There is a significant relationship between PO1 and OT.
- There is a significant relationship between CV1 and OT.
- There is a significant relationship between OT and OCB.
- There is a significant relationship between PO1 and OCB.
- There is a significant relationship between CV1 and OCB.
- There is a significant relationship between A1 and OCB.
- There is a significant relationship between C1 and OCB.
- There is a significant relationship between OCBS1 and OCB.
- There is a significant relationship between OCBC1 and OCB.

Model Fit

	Critical value	Probability level
CMIN	1822.215	.000
RMR	.819	
GFI	.669	
AGFI	.465	
PGFI	.414	
RMSEA	.507	

From the above table it is noted that CMIN, RMR, GFI, AGFI, PGFI, RMSEA has the values 1822.215, .819, .669, .465, .414, .507 respectively, which shows the goodness of fit.

Inference

- It shows the relationship between PJ 1 and OT at .20 level.
- It shows the relationship between CO1 and OT at .11 level.
- It shows the relationship between PO1 and OT at .35 level.
- It shows the relationship between CV1 and OT at .21 level.
- It shows the relationship between OT and OCB at .05 level.
- It shows the relationship between PO1 and OCB at .68 level.
- It shows the relationship between CV1 and OCB at .02 level.
- It shows the relationship between A1 and OCB at .01 level.
- It shows the relationship between C1 and OCB at .01 level.
- It shows the relationship between OCBS1 and OCB at .03 level.
- It shows the relationship between OCBC1 and OCB at .65 level.

Chi Square

Critical value	Probability level
1822.215	.000

From the above table it is inferred that the hypothesis is significant at 1% percent level between Organizational Trust and Organizational Citizenship Behavior and the critical value is 1822.215. So the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Which says that there is a positive relationship between Organizational Trust and Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Correlation

Correlations					
		PO1	PJ1	CO1	OT
PO1	Pearson Correlation	1	.003	.042	.339**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.963	.552	.000
	N	206	206	206	206
PJ1	Pearson Correlation	.003	1	.953**	.347**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.963		.000	.000
	N	206	206	206	206
CO1	Pearson Correlation	.042	.953**	1	.358**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.552	.000		.000
	N	206	206	206	206
OT	Pearson Correlation	.339**	.347**	.358**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	206	206	206	206

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations							
		OCBC1	OCBS1	C1	A1	OCB	CV1
OCBC1	Pearson Correlation	1	.245**	.228**	-.029	.126	-.014
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.001	.674	.072	.840
	N	206	206	206	206	206	206
OCBS1	Pearson Correlation	.245**	1	-.048	-.034	-.026	.174*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.489	.625	.708	.012
	N	206	206	206	206	206	206
C1	Pearson Correlation	.228**	-.048	1	-.005	.122	.202**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.489		.938	.080	.004
	N	206	206	206	206	206	206
A1	Pearson Correlation	-.029	-.034	-.005	1	-.010	.046
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.674	.625	.938		.882	.512
	N	206	206	206	206	206	206
OCB	Pearson Correlation	.126	-.026	.122	-.010	1	.076
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.072	.708	.080	.882		.281
	N	206	206	206	206	206	206
CV1	Pearson Correlation	-.014	.174*	.202**	.046	.076	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.840	.012	.004	.512	.281	
	N	206	206	206	206	206	206

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The above table gives the inter correlation coefficient between the perceived organizational support (PO) with Procedural justice (PJ), Communication (CO1) and Organizational citizenship behavior. There is low correlation between Perceived organizational support (PO) with procedural justice $r = .003$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between Perceived organizational support (PO) with communication $r = .042$ and there is no significant relationship. Perceived organizational support (PO) is highly correlated with organizational trust $r = .339$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level.

There is low correlation between procedural justice with Perceived organizational support (PO) $r = .003$ and there is no significant relationship. Procedural justice is highly correlated with communication $r = .953$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. Procedural justice is highly correlated with organizational trust $r = .347$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level.

There is low correlation between communication with Perceived organizational support (PO) $r = .042$ and there is no significant relationship. Communication is highly correlated with procedural justice $r = .953$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. Communication is highly correlated with organizational trust $r = .358$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level.

Organizational trust is highly correlated with perceived organizational support $r = .339$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. Organizational trust is highly correlated with procedural justice $r = .347$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. Organizational trust is highly correlated with communication $r = .358$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level.

Conscientiousness is highly correlated with sportsmanship $r = .245$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. Conscientiousness is highly correlated with courtesy $r = .228$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. There is low correlation between Conscientiousness with altruism $r = .029$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between Conscientiousness with organizational citizenship behavior $r = .126$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between Conscientiousness with civic virtue $r = .014$ and there is no significant relationship.

Sportsmanship is highly correlated with Conscientiousness $r = .245$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. There is low correlation between sportsmanship with courtesy $r = .048$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between sportsmanship with altruism $r = .034$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between sportsmanship with organizational citizenship behavior $r = .026$ and there is no significant relationship. sportsmanship is correlated with Civic virtue $r = .174$ and the relationship is significant at 5 per cent level.

Courtesy is highly correlated with Conscientiousness $r = .228$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. There is low correlation between courtesy with sportsmanship $r = .048$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between courtesy with altruism $r = .005$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between courtesy with

organizational citizenship behavior $r = .122$ and there is no significant relationship. Courtesy is highly correlated with Civic virtue $r = .202$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. There is low correlation between altruism with Conscientiousness $r = .029$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between altruism with sportsmanship $r = .034$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between altruism with Courtesy $r = .005$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between altruism with organizational citizenship behavior $r = .010$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between altruism with Civic virtue $r = .046$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between organizational citizenship behavior with Conscientiousness $r = .126$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between organizational citizenship behavior with sportsmanship $r = .026$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between organizational citizenship behavior with courtesy $r = .122$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between organizational citizenship behavior with altruism $r = .010$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between organizational citizenship behavior with civic virtue $r = .076$ and there is no significant relationship.

There is low correlation between civic virtue with Conscientiousness $r = .014$ and there is no significant relationship. Civic virtue is correlated with sportsmanship $r = .174$ and the relationship is significant at 5 per cent level. Civic virtue is highly correlated with courtesy $r = .202$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. There is low correlation between civic virtue with altruism $r = .046$ and there is no significant relationship. There is low correlation between civic virtue with organizational citizenship behavior $r = .076$ and there is no significant relationship. Civic virtue is highly correlated with personal life inference with work life $r = .331$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent Level. Work inference with personal life is correlated with job related factors $r = .182$ and the relationship is significant at 5 per cent level. Work inference with personal life is highly correlated with career related factors $r = .278$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. Work inference with personal life is highly correlated with perceived organization support $r = .789$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. There is a low correlation between work inference with personal life and family life related factors $r = .076$. and there is no significant relationship. There is a low correlation between work inference with personal life and work life balance policies $r = .076$. and there is no significant relationship.

There is a low correlation between Personal life inference with family life and job related factors $r = .101$ and there is no significant relationship. Personal life inference with family life is highly correlated with career related factors $r = .310$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. Personal life inference with family life is highly correlated with perceived organization support $r = .479$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent level. There is a low correlation between personal life inference with family life and family life related factors $r = .147$ and there is no significant relationship. There is a low correlation between personal life inference with family life and work life balance policies $r = .152$ and there is no significant relationship.

There is a low correlation between job related factors and career related factors $r=.020$ and there is no significant relationship. Job related factors is highly correlated with perceived organization support $r=.223$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent Level. There is a low correlation between Personal job related factors and family life related factors $r=.136$ and there is no significant relationship. There is a low correlation between Personal job related factors and work life balance policies $r=.094$ and there is no significant relationship.

Career related factors is highly correlated with perceived organization support $r=.318$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent Level. There is a low correlation between career related factors and family life related factors $r=.020$ and there is no significant relationship. There is a low correlation between job related factors and career work life balance policies $r=.020$ and there is no significant relationship.

There is a low correlation between perceived organization support and family life related factors $r=.085$ and there is no significant relationship. Perceived organization support is highly correlated with work life balance policies $r=.219$ and the relationship is significant at 1 per cent Level.

There is a low correlation between family life related factors and work life balance policies $r=.142$ and there is no significant relationship.

CONCLUSION

The study is attempted to assemble both the analytical and empirical benefaction to the current article. First, it increases our understanding of OT in Indian organizations. The research calculates the effect of PJ, POS held by the workers and communication practices on OCB and faith. In this work conditions, where employees added action is beneficial as it adds additional success to organizational performance, this shows the importance of OT in influencing all the variables of OCB. The proportion of the forecaster variable goes ahead to dynamically influence OT and OCB permits professionals to take suitable steps to add the HR practices and organizational design. It has been shown that faith in a company was experienced only when workers had peak levels of POS, PJ and accuracy in information trans missioned by the administration and that faith also contributes towards OCB. Thus with these discoveries, the administration can modify its procedures and system to achieve the wanted outcomes. Understanding of this concept would be much highlights through qualitative as well as quantitative information. Another restriction of this study was the lack of globalist. The outcomes of this analysis cannot be extended to all types of favors and manufacturing organizations, as only software, telecommunication and steel-manufacturing companies were incorporated in the sample, while it is possible that the findings may or may not hold true in other manufacturing or service organizations. Therefore, future research can include companies in different service and manufacturing activities to increase the globalist of the discoveries.

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